

IMPLEMENTATION CHEERLEADERS GAME TO IMPROVE NOUN SPEECH READING COMPETENCE TOWARD CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT

Renny Sri Herdianty (herdiantyrennysri@gmail.com)

School of Postgraduate Studies Indonesia University of Education, Bandung, Indonesia

Abstract

Children with hearing impairment experience problem in verbal communicating, between language and speech. That condition impact from impairment of hearing organ's. When reading speech, kids sometime having a problem reading articulation from opposite who have a talk with. This research aim to discover if there is a impact from a cheerleaders game when increase the ability of reading noun speech to children with hearing impairment. Cheerleaders game are series of activity to integrate several of sensory sense when speech noun with varied moving movement. This research using experiment method with design research one group pretest – post test and also data processing with Wilcoxon test. Research samples are 6 students with hearing impairment at third grade from SLB X. The instrument that used are reading noun speech ability test. Result from data analyzed shows that cheerleaders game application gave a relatively huge contribution at intensify noun speech reading ability is 38,34%, so that cheerleaders game can be used by teacher as an studying alternative in improving noun speech reading ability to children with hearing impairment in SLB.

Measurement with Wilcoxon got $J_{hitung} = 21$ so $J_{tabel} = 0$, that H_0 refused because $J_{hitung} > J_{tabel}$, with the hypothesis that represented at the research can be accepted. This research can be reviewed more with other researcher with sample research that relatively considerable, vocabulary and movement more varied that are adapted with needs, lack of ability also children competence.

Keywords: Cheerleaders Game, Noun Speech Reading, Children with Hearing Impairment.

Introduction

Children with hearing impairment often have wrong habits when they talk especially when spelling some words. That condition is a result from disability hearing organ, causing children with hearing impairment having a trouble in communicating verbally, among others in language and spelling. Sense that can be used for compensating the hearing function is sight sense. Children with hearing impairment is trained to see lip's motion from their opposite talk by using the main tool in seeing that is speech reading. Sadja'ah, E and Sukardi said (1995 : 45) that :

Children with hearing impairment are not / less hearing / catch words or people's conversation from their hearing, they just able to see / catch people conversation or their opposite talk from lip's motion with ability to see (eyes) those eyes that can shift the fuction or cover things that less or can't be reached by their hearing.

When speech reading, children with hearing impairment sometimes experienced difficulty in reading articulation their opponent talk, especially when meet new people.

Condition in the field at SLB X, less understanding in 3 grade-children's spelling in SDLB is in the matter of rithm and beheading of phrase, the relative voice is a bit monotonous and not expresive, also can't resulting the natural color of voice. The other condition, children with hearing impairment also doing some of wrong articulation in articulation in several words like when spelling consonant words, several articulation problem that always be found in children with hearing impairment is wrong spelling habits that cause adduct, omission, distortion, and substitution.

Very complex impact from disability of hearing organ in children with hearing impairment, one of it is in reading ability in spelling noun, beside that spelling some nouns are the most basic language ability. This is match with what Sundoro said (2004:64) explain that :

Creativity that is linked with revealing or explaining something. This language ability starts from giving information about her / him self, explaining simple things, linking words with drawing, explaining words, also understanding and using the language.

From that problem, of course need an effort so children with hearing impairment can get optimal services or practices that can raise ability in reading spelling, so that all people who interact with children with hearing impairment able to understand what he / she means. Teachers should be using some teahing alternative that is expected can help children with hearing impairment in speaking and communicating well. Alternative that can be used is from cheerleaders game.

Cheerleaders game are a kind of game that linked with words, movement, and song. The aim from this game match with that Gordon Lewis and Gunther Bedson said (2004:103) that to raise ability in spealling also raising ability memorizing words in fun teaching environment is from games.

The aim from cheerleading game according to Gordon Lewis and Gunther Bedson (1999:103) specifically that are :

To make a spelling voice's of language pattern that match with the rule. Fuctioning spelling organs that experiencing stiffness.

To make children realize that every spelling pattern if assembled from one and another can cause certain meaning.

Cheerleaders game application inside learning more fun and showing positive progress to development of read spelling ability. So that, need a research more to know how effective cheerleaders game application in raising in speech reading ability especially children with hearing impairment in noun.

Method

This research consist of two research variable, that are free variable and linked variable. Free variable, is variable that influence or that causing a change or make linked variable appear. The free variable on this research is cheerleaders game, and the linked variable is a variable that be affected or that causing because the existence of free variable. Linked variable or behavioral target in this research is Reading Noun Spelling.

Cheerleaders game in this research is a kind of game that linked with word, movement, and song. The teaching's steps are :

Conditioning students with ask to stand and make a circle or half circle.

Motivating Strategy.

Persentation :

- a. Descriptioning cheerleading game scenario to students.
- b. Doing conversation that leads to noun (body parts, fruits, clothes), and descriptioning cheerlearders.

Practice to imitate rough motoric movement.

Practice to imitate tougue's movement.

Practice to imitate lip's movement.

Cheerleaders Leader is spelling noun, are mixed with hands movement and move position.

Students who isn't being cheerleaders, trying to read noun spelling who spelled by cheerleaders leader, also imitating hands movement and move position. Students who can read the spelling well, will be the next leader of cheerleaders. Students who experienced a difficulty in reading spelling talking muscles movement of his / her friend.

Learning evaluation.

Method have been used for this research is experimental method with quantitatif approach. Design of the research uses one group pretes-postes design. Research design pattern in common can be describe like this :

This research is implemented at SLB X in Bandung City, address at Jalan Cicendo No.2 Kelurahan Babakan Ciamis Kecamatan Sumur Bandung Kota Bandung.

Sample in this research is 6 students with hearing impairment 3rd grade SDLB SLB X in Bandung City. Characteristic of the research sample is children with hearing impairment with classification loss ability to hear from low to middle level with receptive

language ability and expressive the subject having a difficulty in reading muscles movement from their talking opponent especially language voice that hasn't seen in the lips, spelling is swallowed or holded in mouth, rithm and phrase beheading isn't right, the voice a bit the same and not expressive, also can't produce natural voice color and spelling words that having adduct, omission, distortion, and substitution.

Instrument in this research is a ability test to reading spelling. Test will be given before and after treatment. The test that will be given before and after treatment is the same test to compare the result before and after treatment is that a change or not in sample research. After the data in this research had been collected, start doing data processing using statistic non parametric with Wilxocon examination.

Result and Discussion Result

Data of Research Result

Result of this research is score reading spelling noun ability enhancement to children with hearing impairment after have been given cheerleaders game. The result of research can be seen in this graph :

Result of Pre Test Before the intervention Cheerleaders Game

Graph 1. shows the scores of ability to read the speech noun in children with hearing impairment before *cheerleaders* game as treatment is given. On the graph, it appears there was some students that ability to read utterance is not optimal, where children still have difficulties when having to read the speech organs interlocutor.

Graph 1 - The Pre Test Scores of Ability Reading Speech Nouns

Result of Post Test After the intervention Cheerleaders Game

Graph 2. shows the scores of ability to read the speech noun in children with hearing impairment after being given *cheerleaders* as intervention. On this graph looks a

relatively significant increase in the ability to read the speech noun. The condition is marked by the acquisition of scores of each individual to reach 9 and 10.

Graph 2 - The Post Test Scores of Ability Reading Speech Nouns

Enhancement of Reading Speech Nouns

The results of pre-test and post-test reading skills of speech noun in children with hearing impairment who received intervention Cheerleaders game improvement can be seen in the chart below:

Graph 3 - Enhancement of Reading Speech Nouns

Graph 3. shows a significant difference in the ability to read the speech noun, which can be seen from the difference in scores of pre-test and post-test in any individual who has increased. In percentage, then to the ability of the average pre-test reached 58.33% while

the value of post test after being given treatment cheerleaders game reached 96.67%, so the increase or the increase reached 38.34%.

Results of Average Pre and Post Test Ability Test Reading Speech Nouns
Graph 4. Shows significant differences after a given intervention cheerleaders games, namely with the increase reached 38.34% from the prior applied cheerleaders games.

Graph 4 - The Scores of Pre Test and Post Test

Hypothesis Testing

The formulation of the hypothesis in this study is "Application of cheerleaders games can improve the ability to read the speech noun (limbs, fruits, clothing) in children with hearing impairment." While the research is as follows statistics :

$$H_0 : M_1 \leq M_2 \leq 0$$

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Explanation :

M_1 □ score after treatment.

M_2 □ score before treatment.

The main hypothesis testing in this study conducted on, with the following criteria decision making :

H_0 rejected : $J_{\text{arithmetic}} > J_{\text{table}}$

H_0 accepted : $J_{\text{arithmetic}} \leq J_{\text{table}}$

Data from pre-test and post-test were as follows :

Data of post test (M_1) : 10, 9, 10, 10, 10, 9

Data of pre test (M_2) : 7, 4, 7, 5, 5, 7

For the purposes of data analysis compiled in tabular form as follows:

Table 1 - Scores of Pre Test and Post Test The Ability of Reading Speech Nouns

No.	Name	M_1	M_2	$(M_1 - M_2)$	Rank $(M_1 - M_2)$	Sign	
						Positive	Negative
1	Aul	10	7	3	4,5	4,5	-
2	Nab	9	4	5	2	2	-
3	Pur	10	7	3	4,5	4,5	-
4	Ris	10	5	5	2	2	-
5	Sya	10	5	5	2	2	-
6	Yan	9	7	2	6	6	-
Total						21	-

Research hypothesis that will be tested in this study is :

H_0 : No effect of the application cheerleaders play in improving the reading skills of speech noun (limbs, fruits, clothing) in children with hearing impairment. "

H_1 : There is the effect of the application of cheerleaders play in improving the reading skills of speech noun (limbs, food, clothing) in children with hearing impairment.

The real level of significance used was $\alpha = 0.05$. Based on the calculations have been done by using test Wilxocon on speech reading skills in children with hearing impairment nouns , calculation of the absolute price is obtained $J_{\text{arithmetic}} = 21$ and based on the criteria Wilxocon test at the 0.05 level with a number N which 6 are obtained $J_{\text{table}} = 0$, then H_0 is rejected because $J_{\text{arithmetic}} > J_{\text{table}}$, thus the hypothesis proposed in this study received. This shows that "there is an influence in the implementation of the game cheerleaders in improving reading skills of speech noun (limbs, fruits, clothing) in children with hearing impairment.

Discussion

Based on testing this hypothesis "There Influence Application Cheerleaders game against Enhancement Reading Speech Nouns (Member Body, Fruits, Clothing) in Children with Hearing Impairment." The statement described the cheerleaders games can improve the

ability to read the speech noun in children with hearing impairment. This is in line with the conditions set out by Gordon Lewis and Gunther Bedson (2004: 103) that "the game cheerleaders to improve the ability to spell, improve speech and improve the ability to remember words in a fun learning atmosphere through the game".

Individuals who received intervention cheerleaders games can be seen an increase in the ability to read the speech from the pre-test to post-test results. Although generally showed an increase, but also realized there are some children who are not stable increase so decreased. The condition occurs because there are some deaf children sampled study his condition is not in optimum condition, as for individuals who showed significant improvement as the Sya, Nab, Ris, where before in the child intervention have problems when they have to read the speech interlocutor because articulation capability interlocutor elusive. Once in the intervention with cheerleaders games, not just the ability to read utterance increased, but also the ability of articulation of every deaf child is making progress. At the time of articulation abilities progress, these conditions will help the interlocutor to understand the intention is uttered, whereas in Aul, Pur, and Yan, the impact of hearing organ malfunction relatively mild in accessing sound, The condition greatly help them on their visual focus articulation and a relatively well make the process more interventions to optimize their speech reading skills are already good.

However, reading the speech has some weaknesses, among others:

Not all of the sounds of language can be seen on the lips.

Not all of the sounds of language are produced by means of articulation (articulator) can be seen by the other person, because it may be the sound of the language generated by the articulator on the inside of the mouth.

The similarity between various forms of the sounds of language, for example bilabial sounds of language would seem to have the same shape of the lips.

The above conditions also affect the child's ability to understand what is being said by the interlocutor. Moreover, the learning process in children with hearing impairment if it is not based on the face, sound, sensory senses that are not optimally integrated, will make the children get bored quickly in the learning process in schools. Therefore, learning through games is one that is relevant to the conditions of children with hearing impairment. Through the game, will be established a number of interactions between peers extensive, which in the process, created a fun activity to be involved directly in it, one of them through the game cheerleaders where the learning process is perceived as an activity that integrates all play together in an optimal sensory senses.

Integration of sensory senses during the learning process when packaged with a game, will make the verbal communication skills of deaf children develop optimally, as well as learning process will be more enjoyable. Obviously with exercises done effectively and sustainably.

Conclusion

Based on the results of research and data analysis has been done by researchers using Wilxocon formula, the result that the game cheerleaders can improve the ability to read the speech noun in children with hearing impairment.

Recommendation

Researchers propose several recommendations, including:

1. For Teachers

The results could be used by teachers as an alternative learning.

2. For Further Research

Researchers can then conduct research with a sample of more and not pegged to the optimization reading speech said, but can be expanded to sentences, passed into paragraphs that describe specific topics and so the level of functioning of the organ of hearing diverse and variations movement relatively more.

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